

Are Unmotivated Students Cultural Critics?

Thomas Falk

Introduction

Every child born into the world should be looked upon by society as so much raw material to be manufactured. Its quality is to be tested. It is the business of society, as an intelligent economist, to make the best of it.

*Lester Frank Ward, Education, circa 1872
(qtd. in Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 125)*

One is far more likely to hear one's child spoken of as 'human capital' than as a citizen in waiting. American public schools have become, above all, a vast, variegated system funneling this human capital into its final destination in the hierarchies of the undemocratic world of modern work.

Robert Westbrook (2005, p. 229)

Today, student motivation, or lack thereof, stands among the preeminent topics of educational research. Students *could* do well in school, but they are just not that into it. We have all known unmotivated and underachieving students, from the elementary school to the university, who are lazy and lacking in healthy work ethics. Perhaps these folks could benefit from a militaristic style education that compels them to develop better attitudes and habits. Others, however, may have good reason not to be motivated to achieve, and educators may do well to consider them as inarticulate cultural critics who reject the horizons of academic achievement handed to them by school and society (See McDermott, 1988).

As we so often hear from politicians, friends, and family members, the point of going to school is to get a good job. Higher degrees afford us greater opportunity and make our country more competitive in the global economy. In one sense, this folk wisdom is sapient. Since its earliest days in America, the schoolhouse has followed the factory. The link between school and work is historically tight and unseverable. Yet this relationship has not primarily served a public interest. By and large, schools have been funded, managed, and imposed by a financial elite upon a begrudging and frequently resistant working class.

Conceptually, I want to consider the unmotivated student in the mold of the modern cultural critic that arose in Europe during the early 19th century. Karl Marx (1818-1883) remains the most highly influential of those critics who gave articulation to the source and nature of the modern malaise. Marx can help us understand the role of the school in reproducing our larger political economy and within this context we can begin to see why it might make sense to call some students cultural critics.

JPSE II (2014)

Metaphysically, Marx understood the world to be composed not of “things,” but rather of processes and relationships, particularly in relation to the economic organization of society. Capitalism existed not just as an economy, but as an entire mode of associated living. Marx saw modern commercial society consisting in two primary and antagonistic roles: *capital* and *labor*. The capitalist invests money, land, or machinery into the production process while the laborer exercises her labor power to create something of value, namely commodities. But the motivations and rationales behind the two roles differ in one all-important way.

Capital’s chief motivation for entering into its relationship with labor is to turn a profit, to get more capital out of the labor process than was invested. And so, as a rule of logic, the capitalist must pay the laborer an amount lesser than the value of her work. This excess value produced by the laborer and accumulated by the capitalist is known as *surplus value* and is the fundamental source of capital growth (Harvey, 1982). By contrast, the laborer enters the production relation out of necessity. Having been dispossessed of her means of subsistence over the course of modern history, the laborer must sell the hours of her life and her capacity to work, the only commodities in her possession, to a boss in exchange for a wage. The will to live drives the laborer to work.

Industry, wrote Marx, functions first and foremost to generate profit for a capitalist. The satisfaction of human needs, therefore, can only ever be an incidental result of the capitalist production process. This is why our culture of material abundance operates according to a logic of scarcity and why farmers are paid to leave their fields fallow while neighbors starve. It is why the devastation of warfare is a “good” thing for those who produce weaponry and why big-box retailers cheer at the news of natural disaster (Cheng, 26 August 2011). Because labor toils to generate profit for a boss rather than to satisfy human need, it has surrendered its intrinsic interest in the work. Labor has become *alienated*.

However, as Marx wrote, the capitalist process does *not* depend on greedy and avaricious individuals. Market economies and the fierce intra-class competition between capitalists select for calculative attitudes that express themselves as greed and avarice (Muller, 2002, p. 240-241, 257, 263-271). The impersonal *role* of capitalist compels bosses to subjugate and exploit labor so as to generate as much profit as possible (Harvey, 1982).

Translated into a more contemporary metaphor, capitalism and its attendant social-economic roles are like software programs that run on the hardware of human beings and institutions. These programs assume material form through the course of our daily lives. The major challenge facing capital is how to get human beings—possessed of real emotions, hopes, and aspirations—to accept the role of labor and believe that their enslavement is freedom. In this task, our history shows, schools have served capital well.

Schools for Slaves

The potential economic value of the Negro population properly educated is infinite and incalculable.... The Negro and the mule is the only combination so far to grow cotton; the South needs him; but the South needs him educated to be a suitable citizen. Properly directed he is the best possible laborer.... He will willingly fill the more menial positions,

JPSE II (2014)

and do the heavy work, at less wages, than the American white man or any foreign race which has yet come to our shores.

*William Baldwin, Rockefeller General Education Board President, 1899
(qtd. in Spivey, 1978, p. 93-94)*

[F]or the American Negro, the last decade of the 19th and the first decade of the 20th centuries were more critical than the Reconstruction years of 1868 to 1876.... This was the age of triumph for big business, for industry, consolidated and organized on a world-wide scale, and run by white capital with colored labor. The Southern United States was one of the most promising fields for this development, with ... a mass of cheap and potentially efficient labor.

W.E.B. Du Bois (1968, p. 229)

American schools have developed in the image of our capitalist economy. Because a plutocracy has sufficiently dominated their resources and leadership, our schools have never truly been public institutions. Throughout the course of American history, significant developments in the schools have followed major changes in the structure and functioning of the capitalist economy. As unrest has grown among increasing numbers of workers forced into the wage market, schools have taken up the task of quelling that unrest and adjusting the working class to its fate.

For instance, wealthy industrialists imposed schooling upon former slaves in the postbellum South for the explicit purpose of reproducing, as closely as possible, the economic conditions of slavery. Subsequently, this same ethos underlay the design, imposition, and management of schools throughout North America. Summarily, the school's historical role has been the reproduction of our socioeconomic class structure within the lives of students. Analysis of this role should force us to radically reconsider the way we understand "public" and "democratic" education.

The way in which William Baldwin referred to the Negro as a "citizen" in the above quotation resonates eerily with the words of Presidents and political leaders of the past several decades. None mentions civics, politics, or even wisdom as criteria. Instead citizenship appears equated to laboring for a low wage and serving the interests of an employer.

To the Southern plantation owner, the slave was a beast of burden, a not-fully-human *thing*. This did not change suddenly following Emancipation and the Civil War. White industrialists continued to see the African American—and all other Americans—as resources to be exploited in the pursuit of capital growth and accumulation. However, the former-slaves' labor power now had to be harnessed without the aid of the leg iron and the lash. Instead mental shackles would have to be formed. This was the principal end to which schools in the South were designed and to which many schools all over the country were eventually put.

As in the North, schools for former slaves were endowed with three principal ambitions: inculcation of the proletarian work ethic, stabilization of the social order, and material uplift of black folk. Samuel Chapman Armstrong, an officer in the Union Army and son of missionaries to Hawaii, founded the Hampton Institute, the principal educational institution for former slaves, in Virginia in 1868. It is important to note that Armstrong, also the Institute's first principal,

JPSE II (2014)

understood blacks to be an inferior race, unsuited for robust citizenship. Their potential contribution to society remained limited, as he saw it, to the performance of menial labor.

Thus the Hampton Institute sought to train African-Americans in subservience, political quietude, and industry (Spivey, 1978, p. 3-9). (Mis)educated in this way, the former slaves' labor power could be harnessed and their threat to social stability mitigated. Hampton sold and leased black men to Northern businesses as day laborers and strikebreakers. The school's newspaper, *Southern Workman*, featured propaganda extolling the virtues of hard work while demonizing organized labor and black intellectualism (Spivey, 1978, p. 20, 26). Students learned "respect for law" and "proper regard for authority" (p. 27). They were dissuaded from voting and told that Jesus and God are white (p. 30-31). "If Negroes don't get any better education than Armstrong is giving them," remarked William Davis, an emancipated Virginian, "they may as well have stayed in slavery" (qtd. in Spivey, 1978, p. 36).

Nevertheless, Armstrong's star pupil, Booker T. Washington, shined in this environment and brought the Hampton ethos with him to the Tuskegee Institute. At the turn of the 20th century, Washington became the first African-American to visit the White House with an invitation from President Teddy Roosevelt. Rockefeller and J. P. Morgan kept him in regular social company. By awarding Washington a guaranteed lifetime income, Andrew Carnegie laid claim to the icon that legitimized capital's exploitation of black labor in America (Spivey, 1978, p. 94).

Like his mentor, Armstrong, Washington decried the academic mission of Northern black colleges such as Howard, Fisk, and Wilberforce. He hoped that whites would simply leave blacks alone in their humble quietude. Washington implored African Americans to mind the color line by refraining from politics and intellectualism. Thus we find him expounding the same peculiar notion of Negro citizenship as William Baldwin. The greatest contribution the African American could make to society, according to Washington, was economic production. As McWilliams (21 February 21 2005) put it, Washington believed that the profit motive moved America. Within such a society, black people's exploitability could serve as their greatest source of strength. African-Americans and Caucasians, he thought, would do best to maintain separate, peaceful lives and cultures, only meeting and interacting impersonally within the commercial sphere.

Surveys of Tuskegee described a militaristic and harshly disciplinarian institution. Unwarranted searches and seizures of students and their belongings constituted regular parts of daily life and official policy. Many students rebelled, going so far as to call Washington a "slave-master." W. T. B. Williams, with the General Board of Education, found that many students could hardly read or write (Spivey, 1978, p. 53-60). Perhaps exactly for this reason, both Northern and Southern industrialists deeply appreciated the Tuskegee students. After all, as white Southern spokesman William Trent said in regard to black students, "a little learning is a dangerous thing" (qtd. in Spivey, 1978, p. 86).

By the late 19th century, American industry, North and South, was swimming in excess capital and on the lookout for new sources of labor to exploit. A host of wealthy tycoons and magnates, including George Peabody, John Rockefeller, and Andrew Carnegie, found Tuskegee to be an indispensable source of docile, compliant, and zealous workers unlikely to strike or unionize

JPSE II (2014)

(Spivey, 1978, p. 77-88). Together with organizations such as the Southern Improvement Company, these men poured vast sums of money into building up an educational Southern infrastructure according to the Hampton and Tuskegee models (p. 99-101).

These same logics and rationales drove the creation and reform of schools in the North. In most cases, wealthy industrialists supported, funded, and directed the institutionalization of compulsory education. Naturally, members of the working class saw merit in schools. However, they resented the fact that they could exercise little if any control or oversight. The schools' organization and leadership remained far from democratic as neither teachers, nor students, nor community members exercised substantial say regarding their daily operations or ultimate purposes.

W. E. B. Du Bois understood how Hampton, Tuskegee, and Booker T. Washington fit into the larger capitalist economy, treating both students and teachers as objects to be exploited. No people, Du Bois argued, could ever achieve their full potential by accepting the social role of economic resource. Democratic citizenship could not be reconciled with bald commercialism. Not just blacks, but all colors and nationalities of people, needed "the broader, deeper, higher culture of gifted minds and pure hearts," he wrote in *The Souls of Black Folk*, first published in 1903. "[E]lse what shall save us from a second slavery?" (Du Bois, 2005, p. 19, 14).

"The Education Frontier"

The people have the power, and if they are not instructed to sympathize with the intelligent, reading, trading, and governing class, inspired with a taste for the same competitions and prizes, they will upset the fair pageant of Judicature, and perhaps lay a hand on the sacred muniments of wealth itself, and new distribute the land.

Ralph Waldo Emerson (9 December 1841)

I do not know any school system in the United States which is run for the benefit of the children. They are all run for the benefit of the gang.

John Tildsey, New York City Schools Superintendent (qtd. in Sinclair, 1922, p. ix)

19th-century capitalists in Europe, Canada, and America found schooling to be an effective and efficient means for equipping young persons with the habits and mentalities appropriate to the work of industrial labor, meanwhile disrupting the transmission and maintenance of the laboring class' traditional artisanal and craft skills. In school, students learned the compliance and obedience required within modern hierarchical structures of authority; literacy fitted them with the technological capacity to adapt to the changing demands of industrial machinery (Graff, 1991). Often members of the laboring class recognized this and therefore resisted schooling fiercely (Urban & Wagoner, 2004, p. 171).

In order to understand contemporary American education through the Marxian lens, we must look to economic relationships at all levels. How are individual teachers, students, and university faculty connected to and through capital? The Common School of the 19th century is best understood as a political and intellectual cousin to the Hampton and Tuskegee schools. Both terms "public" and "democratic," when used to describe American schools, are misnomers.

JPSE II (2014)

Rather than public and/or democratic control we frequently find domination by a ruling capitalist class combined with begrudging working-class acceptance of schooling as a least-worst alternative. Progressive Era reforms re-shaped schools to fit the needs of capital, namely by adjusting a disgruntled and growing class of wageworkers to the miserable realities of the new economy.

Early America entertained competing visions of the Common School, namely two different conceptions of what folks wanted education to be and do for them. After examining the political-economic effects of the Common School during the First American Republic, I argue that the Progressive Era reforms of American schools represented a capitalist strategy for quelling the rising militancy of a growing wage labor class. Hence the early-20th century became the era of the educational frontier, where capitalist mythology cast the school as proving grounds of the meritocracy and avenue to the American Dream.

During the First Republic we find two alternative visions of the Common School. First and foremost, wealthy industrialists appreciated the schools' inculcation of bourgeois-liberal ideology, by which I mean a constellation of attitudes, understandings, and habits of mind conducive to the smooth functioning of the capitalist political economy. In *The Literacy Myth* (1991), Ohio State University professor Harvey Graff explains that the extension of literacy to the public, through schools, as a means of personal uplift and empowerment, is an apocryphal, although common, conception. Despite their support and endowment of schools, members of the ruling class feared literacy as a potentially subversive tool. Yet it was necessary for the large-scale extension of a moral economy of discipline, docility, and individualistic ambition (Graff, 1991, p. 26-28). Graff (p. 232-233) writes:

In North America, education could replace the coercion of English labor to strict factory rules and internalized self-discipline. In the long run, education was more effective and efficient than overt coercion; certainly, it was less disruptive. The provision of mass schooling; the working class' acceptance of it, though a questioning one; and universal, public education all served this direction: promoting discipline, morality, and the 'training in being trained' that mattered most in the creation and preparation of a modern industrial and urban work force. These were the purposes of the school—and one use of literacy.

Essentially, schooling made for the efficient adjustment of traditional and peasant peoples to proletarian wagedom.

During the Middle Ages, poor peasants could understand severe inequality as part of God's divine plan. But in a modern world lacking such a cosmology, what would defend the aristocrat's hoarded riches from the masses? During the mid-19th century, the American ruling class discovered that mass schooling could invest students with the appropriate ideology, including a sense of naturalness and properness regarding the uneven distribution of wealth and lifestyle. In other words, schooling habituated the children of the working class to the rules, roles, and structures of capitalism. Thomas Cooper stated the same in his *Lectures on Elements of Political Economy* (1826):

JPSE II (2014)

Education universally extended throughout the community will tend to disabuse the working class of people in respect of a notion that has crept into the minds of our mechanics and is gradually prevailing, that manual labor is at present very inadequately rewarded, owing to combinations of the rich against the poor; that mere mental labor is comparatively worthless; that property or wealth ought not be accumulated or transmitted; that to take interest on money lent or profit on capital employed is unjust.... The mistaken and ignorant people who entertain these fallacies as truths will learn, when they have the opportunity of learning, that the institution of political society originated in the protection of property. (Qtd. in Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 178)

An adherent to Hobbesian political economy, Cooper had no use for notions of class warfare and sought explicitly to stamp such notions out from the minds of working-class children.

Addressing the Massachusetts Board of Education in 1842, Horace Mann quoted local industrialist H. Bartlett: "The great majority always have been and probably always will be comparatively poor, while a few will possess the greatest share of this world's goods" (qtd. in Urban & Wagoner, 2004, p. 100-101). Speaking to a capitalist audience in 1844, Mann spoke plainly of schools as purveyors of ruling-class hegemony:

Finally, in regard to those who possess the largest shares in the stock of worldly goods, could there, in your opinion, be any police so vigilant and effective, for the protection of all the rights of person, property and character, as such a sound and comprehensive education and training as our system of common schools could be made to impart.... Would not the payment of a sufficient tax to make such training universal, be the cheapest means of self-protection and insurance? (Qtd. in Urban & Wagoner, 2004, p. 100-101)

Such overtures contrasted sharply with the logic and appeal Mann presented to Massachusetts's working class.

In the second vision of the Common School, members of the working class remained divided in their support. Many resisted schooling as an imposition upon their way of life and regarded the schools' capitalist purveyors more as invading conquerors than as members of their communities. Others appreciated the schools' effect of thinning out the labor pool by removing children from the workforce and driving up wages. Many placed their hopes in Mann's rhetoric of social advancement through education.

The first half of the 19th century saw a widespread and unprecedented shift from small proprietorship to wage work, particularly in Northeastern industrial towns. The Common School shift in social relations of reproduction, from mixed-age to age-graded groupings, mirrored the concomitant shift in relations of material production from the home and independent shop to the factory. That is, the social relations of schooling came to mirror less the home and more the corporation. As large-scale factories pushed independent proprietors out of the marketplace, folks were left with few choices but to willingly enlist as wageworkers. Within this new economic structure, schooling came to appear to the working class as the last viable means of social advance.

JPSE II (2014)

According to the socio-economic cosmology of antebellum America, wagedom constituted a temporary stage to be endured and surpassed on the road to economic independence. Perhaps this is what Horace Mann believed. On his tours throughout New England, he preached a rhetoric of upward mobility to his working-class audiences. The school, he told them, would prevent the hardening of class lines as well as “the domination of capital and the servility of labor” (qtd. in Urban & Wagoner, 2004, p. 103). Most famously, in his Twelfth Annual Report to the Massachusetts School Board, he stated that “Education ... beyond all other devices of human origin, is the great equalizer of the conditions of men—the balance wheel of the social machinery” (qtd. in Urban & Wagoner, 2004, p. 103). By working hard and proving their merit in school, individuals could escape wagedom and join the owning class. This hope proved a savory tonic for the dispossessed people of New England who lacked alternative paths to redemption.

The mercurial Horace Mann sold the Common School to both the wealthy and working classes: for the latter as an institution of social uplift and for the former to secure private property and promote social stability by quelling inter-class hostility. Most historians agree that Mann was a conservative in the traditional sense, wanting to preserve the social structure in which he had grown up and believing in the Common School as a force for stability (Urban & Wagoner, 2004; Bowles & Gintis, 1977; Westbrook, 2005). Yet there are two ways in which we are forced to conclude that Mann’s overtures to the working class were disingenuous.

First, belief in social mobility as a legitimate possibility for most Americans was already becoming untenable in his time; it simply did not match up with the empirical facts. Second, and most glaringly, he had to know that the capitalist class would ultimately control and shape the schools. The working class was neither wealthy nor politically powerful enough to exert much influence over the aims, purposes, and conduct of schooling. For example, during its first three decades, 85 percent of Lowell, Massachusetts school board members hailed from the business and professional class; less than five percent came from the working class (Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 163). It requires a tremendous acrobatics of mind to believe that Mann truly expected the Common School to promote social and economic democracy.

Although farmers and immigrants did not oppose schooling in principle, they wanted the self-determination to control their own schools. In Beverly, Massachusetts, in the year 1860, more than three-quarters of the town’s working population voted against establishing a school. These were once-independent shoemakers who had been forced out of the marketplace by and into large textile factories (Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 155-156). The transition from independent proprietorship to proletarian wage work wrought devastating effects upon the quality of their lives, robbing them of control over production schedules and the daily rhythms of work. By resisting school, they sought to protect their children from an institution understood to be aligned with the designs of their employing masters.

When Irish immigrants of Lowell boycotted the schools, the State hired truant officers to forcibly bring children in and arrest recalcitrant parents. Similar developments repeated across the state (Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 164). Populist revolts slowed down the establishment of schools in Minnesota, Nebraska, Kansas, Alabama, North Carolina, and the Dakotas; but resistance

JPSE II (2014)

inevitably gave way. In areas of the country where wage labor had not yet taken hold, few saw reasons for building schools. Yet wherever factories grew up and men and women entered the ranks of wagedom, schools soon followed (p. 176-177).

Writing from the Regina Coeli prison in Rome during the 1920's, Antonio Gramsci argued that no regime, no matter how authoritarian, could long sustain itself through overt coercion and violence. It is necessary, he believed, that popular support and legitimacy be contained in a system of values, attitudes, beliefs, and morals that pervades society as a natural order (Burke, 2005). Nothing about schools implicates them as necessarily coercive. Yet, as a State institution, the school may become just as coercive as judicial, police, or military forces.

During the Progressive Era, as corporate capitalism eclipsed the older, small-scale competitive economy, professional administrators and businessmen liquidated nearly all that remained of working-class representation on urban school boards (Carnoy, 1972, p. 3). In reaction to growing populist revolt against the swelling prevalence of wage work and the increasingly clear rigidity of class divisions, Progressive school reforms sought again to reduce social tension by adjusting the proletariat to its fate. Here the mission of the school grew in scope and magnitude to become an indispensable and permanent division of labor in the reproduction of the larger political economy. Responding to massive labor strikes across the country, capitalists restored order by calling in strikebreakers, Pinkerton thugs, and the National Guard to beat, shoot, and murder workers. But industrialists such as Carnegie believed that the true solution to the unrest lay in "education, education, education" (Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 18).

At the time of the American Revolution, 80 percent of non-slave adult males remained independent property owners and proprietors. That number fell to 33 percent by 1880 (Bowles & Gintis, 1977, p. 59). During the decade just prior to the turn of the 20th century it had become apparent that wagedom was a lasting and even permanent condition for most Americans. From that point on, very few ever graduated to the ranks of independent proprietorship. Men and women had to accept competing against each other within corporations rather than competing against the corporations themselves. Once again, school appeared to the working class as the last viable means for improving one's competitive chances.

Revolving Doors and Dirty Pipelines

[S]chools have evolved in the United States not as a pursuit of equality, but rather to meet the needs of capitalist employers for a disciplined and skilled labor force, and to provide a mechanism for social control in the interests of political stability.... Although the unequal distribution of political power serves to maintain inequalities in education, the origins of these inequalities are to be found outside the political sphere, in the class structure itself and in the class subcultures typical of capitalist societies. Thus, unequal education has its roots in the very class structure which it serves to legitimize and reproduce. Inequalities in education are part of the web of capitalist society, and are likely to persist as long as capitalism survives.

Samuel Bowles (1972, p. 36-37)

JPSE II (2014)

In our country's educational system the capitalist class now walks through a revolving door between high positions in the private and governmental sectors. Meanwhile a vastly increasing number of our poorest students, from the ages of five and six, are sent down the school-to-prison pipeline. Just as they did a century ago, today's plutocrats dominate American schools, making decisions as to how they will function, what will be taught, and which aims will be pursued. Educators must struggle against the institutionalized logic of capital that sees students as beasts of burden, resources to be exploited for the purpose of capital growth and accumulation. To the great extent that schooling succeeds in reproducing a stratified economic class structure and the constitution of human persons suited to its roles, democratic citizenship will be precluded as an aim of American education.

Writing in *Dissent* magazine, Joanne Barkan (Winter 2011) describes a contemporary plutocratic dominance of schools, a multi-billionaire triumvirate of capitalists—including Bill Gates, the Walton family, and Eli Broad—as the tail that wags the dog of American education. Through their foundations this tiny cabal of plunderers has strategically pushed privatization, choice, accountability, competition, deregulation, merit pay, and high-stakes testing down the throats of our nation's teachers and students. Through their ownership of national media, they have shaped public dialogue and sold their designs to the American people. Rather than improving education, their programs have tyrannized our most promising teachers and terrorized a generation of the doomed.

Public schooling is a half-trillion dollar annual venture in America. As of 2010, the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, backed by a matching donation from Warren Buffett, boasted a \$63 billion endowment. Together with the multi-billion dollar endowments of the Eli & Edy Broad Foundation and the Walton Family Foundation, Gates directs public policy and shapes the composition of the educational workforce. For instance, at the Broad Superintendents Academy, pliable business and legal executives are recruited and trained to implement the Foundation's agenda into urban school districts. In 2009, with the help of Broad's supple political and financial connections, the academy's graduates filled a stunning 43 percent of all open superintendencies across the nation's large urban school districts (Barkan, Winter 2011). As an example of what the plutocracy has in store, we can look to the Chicago Public Schools' *Renaissance2010* project, also known as *Ren2010*.

In 1995 the Gates Foundation gave Chicago Public Schools Chief Executive Officer Arne Duncan \$90 million to turn the failing institution around. Duncan had been installed with the help of the Commercial Club of Chicago (CCC), an organization of the city's top financial, corporate, and political elites. Along with the money, Gates gave Duncan a how-to manual titled *The Turnaround Challenge*, which laid out a path toward raising educational achievement through choice, accountability, high-stakes testing, and privatization. According to Chicago residents, *Ren2010* put tremendous pressure on schools to achieve academic goals for which they lacked the necessary resources (Lipman & Haines, July 2007, p. 490). School failure, with the legal consequence of privatization, was assured from the start. Under the benevolent guise of "saving the children," education, the process of constituting young human beings, was wrested from public oversight and handed to the forces of the market.

JPSE II (2014)

Respectively professors at the University of Illinois at Chicago and DePaul University, Pauline Lipman and Nathan Haines (Lipman & Haines, July 2007, p. 490) write that *Ren2010* constituted only one division of a larger plan to convert the city into a more efficient engine of capital growth. For 25 years, Chicago's working-class residents had been foreclosed upon and forced out of the city in order to make room for upscale residential and commercial space (p. 485-493). This gentrification process began, reports Chicago resident and investment banking heir Karl Muth, by building police stations in the neighborhoods, tearing out basketball courts, and closing down the public schools (Johnson, 2006). The now-privatized schools existing on the margins of this gentrified space are currently training the children of the poor and working class in the basic, low-grade skills appropriate to the space's low-paying service sector jobs. Effectively, the Gates Foundation, the CCC, and Arne Duncan have created a network of collection bins for Chicago's economic refuse to be recycled into useful, low-wage servants of capital.

Promptly after President Barack Obama nominated him as Secretary of the U.S. Department of Education, Duncan created the position of Director of Philanthropic Engagement, making private foundation partnerships the hallmark of his DOE stewardship. "[T]he Department is 'open for business,'" he announced in an October, 2009 issue of the DOE newsletter, *The Education Innovator*. But Duncan is by no means the lone Black Hand affiliate occupying top positions in the DOE. Margot Rogers, Duncan's first chief of staff, worked for Gates, as did her replacement, Joanne Weiss. Russlynn Ali, Assistant Secretary for Civil Rights, is a former employee of both Broad and Gates. General Counsel Charles Rose and Assistant Deputy Secretary for Innovation and Improvement James Shelton both worked for Gates. Even Larry Summers, former Treasury Secretary and President of Harvard University, sat on the Broad Foundation's board of directors. Collectively, this team designed the Obama administration's *Race to the Top* program according to the philosophy of Gates's *Turnaround Challenge*, which Duncan hails as "the bible" of school restructuring.

It is impossible to separate government from corporate entities in the realm of American schooling. On the cover of its December 2008 issue, *Time* magazine featured Michelle Rhee, then Chancellor of Washington, D.C. Schools, standing in a classroom holding a broom. Next to her was written in big bold letters: "How To Fix America's Schools." Rhee attempted to implement in the nation's capital a \$63-million Gates-funded strategy of high-stakes testing, accountability, and school closing, earning her the ire of teachers' unions across the country. Although there is little evidence for educational improvement, investigations have discovered massive patterns of teachers cheating on standardized tests: erasing wrong answers and filling in the correct ones, ostensibly in desperate efforts to keep their jobs so that they might continue to bring in paychecks and feed their families (Gillam & Bello, 30 March 2011). Poverty rates are staggering in Washington, D.C. and paying jobs are tough to come by. Yet public support for these misbegotten school reform initiatives remains strong.

Examples of media propaganda such as the *Time* magazine cover work astonishingly well at convincing audiences of their message. Rhee, in an uncomplicated and empowering image, is fixing the crisis in education by sweeping away the garbage, the stupid and lazy teachers. Our plutocracy also contributes millions to most major national education organizations as well as news and media outlets. In 2010 it sponsored NBC's "Education Nation" as well as the renowned propaganda film *Waiting for Superman* (Chilcott, 2010). Both of these programs

JPSE II (2014)

painted pictures of crisis in education and Gates-style reform as the sure-fire solution. Frederick Hess (2005) reports in his book *With the Best of Intentions* that the national press handles the capitalist educational foundations with kid gloves: the *New York Times*, *Los Angeles Times*, *Washington Post*, *Chicago Tribune*, *Newsweek*, and *Associated Press* each publish 13 positive for every one critical article (Barkan, Winter 2011).

In addition to the major educational foundations, Coca-Cola, McDonald's, Exxon, and Hershey dump enormous funding into cash-strapped schools. But the money does not come unattached. In exchange, schools must conduct lessons provided by the Hershey Corporation about the importance of chocolate in a balanced diet. Teachers in business classes must instruct students in how to apply for and manage a McDonald's franchise. McDonald's-sponsored physical education programs conducted in 31 thousand schools nationwide instantiate brand loyalty into developing citizen-consumers. Elsewhere, teachers must conduct an environmental curriculum from Shell Oil extolling the virtues of the external combustion engine (Farahmandpur, 2010, p. 63-64).

Students of America's underfunded schools make easy prey for the corporatocracy in the same way that impoverished children of the world make easy prey for sex traffickers. The moneyed interests in this relationship know that their beneficiaries are desperate and effectively hostage. Reflecting on these types of "educational" programs, Charles Sullivan writes:

Of course it is not in the self-interest of capitalism to educate people who can see capitalism for what it is, to think critically about it, and perhaps even do something to change it. Corporate education exists to promote programming consumers and providing an obedient workforce to an unfair slave wage system, not to provide society with a well-informed and politically active citizenry. In fact these are the things that pose the greatest threat to America's corporate oligarchy. (Qtd. in Farahmandpur, 2010, p. 65).

The problem with private organizations taking charge of our schools, whether for-profit or philanthropic, is that they allow for little democratic oversight or control. People far removed from students and classrooms impose their decisions upon educators with impunity. In districts where constituents are not vigilantly engaged in their children's education, the logic of capital wreaks soul-crushing havoc.

It is ironic, writes Jonathan Kozol, that wherever you find a school named after a Civil Rights leader—Martin Luther King, Jr., Rosa Parks, or Thurgood Marshall, for example—it will almost uniformly be as segregated as schools of the 1950's. Newer and equally segregated schools carry names such as Academy of Enterprise and Corporate Academy. These "industry-imbedded" schools funnel poor students into low-paying jobs. In Columbus, Ohio, for example, young students are asked to choose their careers while sitting inside classroom walls lined with posters from JC Penny, Wal-Mart, Kmart, and Sears. Company-scripted lesson plans compel students to act out the roles of cashier and manager. "I'm in the business of developing minds to meet a market demand," states one Chicago school principal whose school's contract with its curriculum design company stipulates that agents will visit and police classrooms to ensure teachers stick to their scripts, a practice eerily reminiscent of the Soviet schools under Stalin (Kozol, 2005, p. 89-103).

JPSE II (2014)

Kozol describes Taylorism and Skinnerian behavioral modification pedagogies dominating impoverished and heavily segregated classrooms. “Do exactly what I say, when I say it, and you’ll get it right. Otherwise, you’ll get it wrong,” one teacher told her fourth-grade students at one of these privately-run schools in New York City (Kozol, 2005, p. 64). There and elsewhere Kozol observed direct-command, rote-and-drill pedagogies featuring the terminology of business and commerce. Students spent hours forming and standing in lines before enduring silent lunches and recesses. One principal, Mr. Endicott, referred to his school’s curriculum as “horrific for the teachers and boring for the children ... an intellectual straight jacket” (Kozol, 2005, p. 89). Here, where parents are not highly involved and education is turned over to the profit motive, teachers become stifled by rigidly prescribed standards and curricula; their students receive an education suitable for a life of poverty in the dregs of the economy.

Rania Khalek reports that at the same time more students than ever are being suspended, expelled, and even sent from school to prison as a result of zero-tolerance policies adopted by 80 percent of the nation’s schools during the 1990’s. High school freshmen have been convicted of felonious assault for stealing lunch money from classmates. Police are arresting and interrogating students for writing on their desks and handcuffing kindergartners who throw tantrums (Khalek, 8 August 2011). According to Chris McGreal of the *Guardian*, during the 2010 school year police in the state of Texas handed out close to 300 thousand “Class C misdemeanor” tickets to children as young as six, which involved fines, community service, and even prison sentences for “crimes” as innocuous as “disrupting class” or throwing paper airplanes (McGreal, 9 January 2012).

Increasingly, police officers conduct regular patrols of schools armed with pepper spray, handcuffs, and handguns (Khalek, 21 December 2011). Although it is not the only state to do so, the number of school districts in Texas with their own police departments has risen more than 20-fold since 2001 (McGreal, 9 January 2012). There, police are disproportionately confronting, detaining, tasing, and arresting poor, disabled, and minority students of color. Statistics show that school punishment correlates to later involvement with the criminal justice system (Khalek, 8 August 2011). As young children are branded “troublemakers,” they find themselves increasingly targeted for “correction” by State institutions. Texas supreme court chief justice Wallace Jefferson warns that “[c]harging kids with criminal offenses for low-level behavioral issues” is likely driving many of them into a life of imprisonment (McGreal, 9 January 2012). Across the country, students are growing accustomed to penal-colony-style regimes of surveillance, discipline, and punishment. Many of those who do not grow up to serve their purposes as JC Penny cashiers or Wal-Mart shelf-stockers will end up in the nation’s sprawling prison labor camps.

In fact, the prostitution of prisoner-laborers is now a multi-billion dollar industry in most U.S. states. According to the *Wall Street Journal*, 37 states currently allow corporations to pay prison laborers between one and five dollars per day, while federal prisons pay 25 cents to \$1.25 per hour (Silver-Greenberg, 2011). These prisoners are not just making license plates anymore. They operate call-centers for cable companies and take reservations for American Airlines. The list of major corporations employing prisoners includes IBM, Boeing, Motorola, Microsoft, AT&T Wireless, Texas Instruments, Dell, Compaq, Honeywell, Hewlett-Packard, Nortel, Lucent

JPSE II (2014)

Technologies, 3Com, Intel, Northern Telecom, Nordstrom's, Revlon, Macy's, Target, and others. Altogether, the prison-industrial complex now employs close to one million full-time workers and generates \$2.4 billion in annual revenue (Khalek, 21 July 2011).

Unmotivated to Achieve

Faced with the unsatisfactory and indeed politically motivated paradigms of explanation that have been insinuated into the mental fiber of modern capitalist society ... what counterstrategy is available for the illumination of reality that does not in some subtle way replicate its ruling ideas, its dominant passions, and its enchantment of itself? As I see it, this question is both necessary and utopian. It is essential to pose the challenge, but it is utopian to believe that we can imagine our way out of our culture without acting on it in practical ways that alter its social infrastructure. For this reason, what I call negative criticism is all that is possible, apt, and demanded at the intellectual level.

Michael Taussig (1980, p. 7)

According to the anthropologist David Harvey, capital exercises its power over labor at the level of ideas. Particularly, the Enlightenment conception of the human being as an individual, self-sufficient, pre-social entity prevents members of the laboring class from recognizing their mutual interests in relation to capital (Harvey, 5 July 2009). For example, many of the families and individuals detrimentally impacted by the recent financial crisis, who have lost homes and jobs, blame only themselves and their own private lack of ability, intelligence, or hard work. This incapacity to recognize larger patterns and structures represents a major conceptual and educational crisis. As long as workers continue to fight for their own private piece of the pie, we will forever remain impotent before capital's immense power.

A Marxist interpretation of these ideas might argue that current educational policy constructs academic achievement as a private and individual attainment, all to the detriment of the laboring class. Standardized tests, now almost universally accepted as the ultimate measure of academic achievement, trace their intellectual history to early-20th century educational psychologists such as David Snedden and Edward Thorndike. Under the authority of science, Thorndike promised educators the capacity to accurately measure and scale the quality and contents of individual minds. Intelligence tests, crafted to produce a distribution of outcomes, provided a model for conceiving learning as a private, cognitive act. Because of its reincarnation as "achievement" and "proficiency tests" in our schools today, academic failure remains for many a pre-determined institutional outcome yet continues to be misunderstood as a result of private ineptitudes and pathologies on the part of individual students and teachers. More complex and systemic factors remain largely insensible.

Research suggests that this current model for learning disproportionately impinges upon the students and teachers of poor and minority schools. Michelle Fine, of the City University of New York, has written that the institutional rhetoric of academic achievement within many poor and urban schools serves to unduly privatize and psychologize what in reality are complex and systematic social problems (Fine, February 1987). Analogous to Fine's description, the failure of Chicago Public Schools under the auspices of *Ren2010* has officially been blamed not on resource deficiencies, but on the ineptitudes of individual students, teachers, parents, and

JPSE II (2014)

communities. Furthermore, she reports, the tremendous legal and political pressure placed on poor urban schools to score well on standardized tests forces them to exclude from the curriculum the problems and concerns of students' daily lives, whether these be gangs, poverty, sports or poetry. Fine's research uncovers on a local scale what has been a widespread effect of national policy on urban education: a wholesale exclusion of the vital, social worlds of students from the territory of knowledge and learning. Rather than assisting students in developing a more sophisticated understanding of the world and their relation to it, the rhetoric of "academic achievement" confines knowledge and learning to a commodified set of skills and information understood to be located within the private, individual mind.

Our contemporary insistence upon academic achievement ignores the school's historical and ongoing involvement in the class war between capital and labor. Thus, we might do well to take some unmotivated and underachieving students as serious individuals who reject the horizons of achievement handed to them by their school and society, and as cultural critics who only lack the more sophisticated powers of articulation wielded by great writers (McDermott, 1988). Some students "act out" in school because they lack the language with which to give expression to their malaise. Others speak with profound articulateness.

It is almost a normative practice in American culture for a child to answer "nothing" to the parent's question, "What did you learn in school today?" Consider that this is a learned behavior, something that a child must learn as an appropriate answer to the question. How would a child learn this? Undoubtedly it is learned from the parents who return home from work every day tired, defeated, and with nothing interesting to report. Children pick up on the fact that most of the jobs in our economy are depressingly dull and monotonous. They understand that the hours between 9am and 5pm are the hours when the spirit dies. Moreover, they sense that their schooling is preparing them to enter this soul-crushing workaday world.

Standing on the steps of U.C. Berkeley's Sproul Hall in December of 1964, Mario Savio pronounced to the gathered crowd:

We have an autocracy which runs this university. It's managed. We asked the following: if President Kerr actually tried to get something more liberal out of the Regents in his telephone conversation, why didn't he make some public statement to that effect? And the answer we received—from a well-meaning liberal—was the following: He said, 'Would you ever imagine the manager of a firm making a statement publicly in opposition to his board of directors?' That's the answer! Now, I ask you to consider: if this is a firm, and if the Board of Regents are the board of directors, and if President Kerr in fact is the manager, then I'll tell you something: the faculty are a bunch of employees, and we're the raw material! But we're a bunch of raw material that don't mean to have any process upon us, don't mean to be made into any product, don't mean to end up being bought by some clients of the University, be they the government, be they industry, be they organized labor, be they anyone! We're human beings!

[Wild applause from the crowd.]

JPSE II (2014)

There is a time when the operation of the machine becomes so odious, makes you so sick at heart, that you can't take part; you can't even passively take part, and you've got to put your bodies upon the gears and upon the wheels, upon the levers, upon all the apparatus, and you've got to make it stop. And you've got to indicate to the people who run it, to the people who own it, that unless you're free, the machine will be prevented from working at all! (Savio, 4 December 1964)

Savio saw himself and his classmates as cogs in an academic-industrial machine. He attended a prestigious university where the next generation of America's corporate bosses would earn their credentials. But Mario and others wanted no part in this. Instead they sought the sort of education that could help them understand and challenge the cruel stupidity of their world.

Conclusion

The clash of cultures in the classroom is essentially a class war, a socio-economic and racial warfare being waged on the battleground of the schools.... [T]his is an uneven balance, particularly since, like most battles, it comes under the guise of righteousness.

Kenneth Clark (1965, p. 129)

Particularly in the decades since the Reagan Revolution, education has been understood in our culture as an individualistic means of getting ahead in life. Gone are the sober hopes that schools, colleges, and universities might play anything but a redundant role in the struggle for social and economic justice. Saddled with unprecedented levels of student debt, today's graduates will be among the last to challenge the power of their capitalist overlords by striking in demand for better wages and working conditions. As for schoolteachers, success has become more than ever defined by the ability to meet goals set by corporate and government entities such as the Gates triumvirate with its strong ties to the Department of Education. Also, for university faculty, a successful career is increasingly defined by one's ability to draw government, corporate, and hybrid corporate-government funding. Marxists might remind us that along with that money and therefore along with our success, we as professional educators become invested with the aims and purposes of our donors. Faculty in colleges and departments of education would do well to ask themselves whether their research contributes in any way to the maligned rhetoric of academic achievement and to the treatment of students as means to the end of capital accumulation.

Regarding students, let me restate that many unmotivated and underachieving students might simply be lazy and lacking in healthy work ethics. These students could perhaps stand to benefit—themselves as well as others—from a militaristic, behavioral-modification style intervention that compels them to develop better habits and mentalities. However, others may have good reason not to be motivated to achieve in school. They may sense that their education has suspiciously little to do with their vital concerns and interests or that as students they are treated as a means to some grim and uncertain end. Nonetheless we cannot call these students cultural critics when their criticisms remain inarticulate.

There are limits to Marxism; synoptic theories-of-everything necessarily distort the world and delude their adherents. Yet Marx, alongside many other critics, gives us a language with which

JPSE II (2014)

to communicate and make sense of the otherwise insensible. I submit that a most worthy aim of education, one with pragmatic and even cash value, is to assist students in the work of understanding the world and their place within it. This work is essentially the work of articulation, of putting the world to language. Indispensably, this requires educators to take into account the native sensibilities and intimations of the young, to consider that some unmotivated students may prove to be our best resources for recognizing the greater maladies of school, culture, and society to which we adults have become inured and therefore accept as natural.¹

References

- Baldwin, W. (1899). The present problem of Negro education. *Journal of Social Science*, 37, 52-68.
- Barkan, J. (2011, Winter). Got dough? How billionaires rule our schools. *Dissent*. Retrieved from <http://dissentmagazine.org/article/?article=3781>.
- Bowles, S. (1972). Unequal education and the reproduction of the social division of labor. In M. Carnoy (Ed.). *Schooling in a corporate society: The political economy of education in America* (pp. 36-64). New York: David McKay, Inc.
- Bowles, S. & Gintis, H. (1977). *Schooling in capitalist America: Educational reform and the contradictions of economic life*. New York: Basic Books.
- Burke, B. (2005). Antonio Gramsci, schooling and education. *Encyclopedia of informal education*. Retrieved from <http://www.infed.org/thinkers/et-gram.htm>.
- Calkins, A., Guenther, W., Belfiore, G. & Lash, D. (2007). *The turnaround challenge*. Mass Insight Education & Research Institute. Retrieved from http://www.massinsight.org/publications/turnaround/51/file/1/pubs/2010/04/15/TheTurnaroundChallenge_MainReport.pdf.
- Carnoy, M. (Ed.). (1972). *Schooling in a corporate society: The political economy of education in America*. New York: David McKay, Inc.
- Cheng, Andria (26 August 2011). Likely retail winners and losers from Irene. *MarketWatch*. Retrieved from http://www.marketwatch.com/story/likely-retail-winners-and-losers-from-irene-2011-08-26?link=MW_latest_news.
- Chilcott, L. (Producer) & Guggenheim, D. (Director). (2010). *Waiting for 'Superman'* [Motion picture]. United States: Paramount Vantage.
- Clark, K. (1989). *Dark ghetto: The dynamics of social power*. Middletown, CT: Wesleyan University Press. (Original work published 1965).
- Cooper, T. (1826). *Lectures on the elements of political economy*. Columbia, SC: D. E. Sweeney. Retrieved from <http://deila.dickinson.edu/theirrownwords/title/0039.htm>.
- Du Bois, W. E. B. (1968). *The autobiography of W.E. Burghardt Du Bois*. New York: International Publishers.
- Du Bois, W. E. B. (2005). *The souls of Black folk*. New York: Barnes & Noble Classics.
- Duncan, A. (29 October 2009). Shooting for the moon: A joint venture. *The Education Innovator*, 7 (8). U.S. Department of Education, Office of Innovation and Improvement. Retrieved from <http://www2.ed.gov/news/newsletters/innovator/2009/1029.pdf>.
- Education nation: Teacher town hall. (2011, September 25). [Television broadcast]. NBC News. Retrieved from: <http://www.educationnation.com/index.cfm?objectid=F0E4CA30-D338-11E0-810D000C296BA163>.

JPSE II (2014)

- Emerson, R. W. (9 December 1841). The conservative. Masonic Temple, Boston. Retrieved from <http://www.vcu.edu/engweb/transcendentalism/authors/emerson/essays/conservative.html>.
- Farahmandpur, R. (2010). Teaching against consumer capitalism in the age of commercialization and corporatization of public education. In J. Sandlin & P. McLaren (Eds.). *Critical pedagogies of consumption: Living and learning in the shadow of the "shopocalypse."* (pp. 58-66). New York: Routledge.
- Fine, M. (February 1987). Silencing in public schools. *Language Arts*, 64 (2), 157-174.
- Gillam, J. & Bello, M. (30 March 2011). When standardized test scores soared in Washington, D.C., were the gains real? *USA Today*. Retrieved from http://www.usatoday.com/news/education/2011-03-28-1Aschooltesting28_CV_N.htm.
- Graff, H. (1991). *The literacy myth: Cultural integration and social structure in the nineteenth century*. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction Publishers. (Original work published 1979).
- Harvey, D. (1982). *The limits to capital*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Harvey, D. (Creator). adycousins (Poster). (5 July 2009). The crisis today: Marxism 2009. [Video]. Bloomsbury. Retrieved from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YYQb0fthNfI>.
- Hess, F. (Ed.). (2005). *With the best of intentions: How philanthropy is reshaping K-12 education*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Education Press.
- Johnson, J., Kurzon, N. (Producers), & Johnson, J. (Director). (2006). *The one percent* [Motion picture]. United States: HBO Documentary Films.
- Khalek, R. (21 July 2011). 21st-Century slaves: How corporations exploit prison labor. *AlterNet*. Retrieved from www.alternet.org/story/151732/.
- Khalek, R. (8 August 2011). 8 years in prison for a harmless prank? Handcuffed for doodling? The increasing criminalization of students. *AlterNet*. Retrieved from <http://www.alternet.org/story/151948/>.
- Khalek, R. (21 December 2011). Madness: Even school children are being pepper-sprayed and shocked with tasers. *AlterNet*. Retrieved from <http://www.alternet.org/story/153536/>.
- Kilpatrick, W. H. (1969). *The educational frontier*. New York: Arno Press.
- Kozol, J. (1975). *The night is dark and I am far from home*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Kozol, J. (2005). *The shame of the nation: The restoration of apartheid schooling in America*. New York: Crown Publishers.
- Lipman, P. & Haines, N. (July 2007). From accountability to privatization and African American exclusion: Chicago's "Renaissance 2010." *Educational Policy*, 21 (3), 471-502.
- Mann, H. (1972). Fifth annual report, 1842. In M. Katz (Ed.). *School reform: Past and present*. Boston: Little & Brown.
- Mann, H. (1975). Twelfth annual report, 1848. In L. Cremin (Ed.). *The republic and the school: Horace Mann on the education of free men*. New York: Teachers College Press.

JPSE II (2014)

- McDermott, R. (1988). Inarticulateness. In D. Tannen (Ed.). *Linguistics in context: Connecting observation and understanding* (pp. 37-68). Norwood, NJ: Ablex Publishing Corporation.
- McGreal, C. (9 January 2012). The US schools with their own police. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/2012/jan/09/texas-police-schools>.
- McWilliams, C. (21 February 2005). American political thought since the Civil War: Progressivism and W. E. B. Du Bois. Audio recording. Haverford College. Retrieved from <http://www.haverford.edu/politicalscience/faculty/mcwilliams/pols268/index.php>.
- Muller, Jerry (2002). *The Mind and the Market: Capitalism in Modern European Thought*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Savio, M. (4 December 1964). Mario Savio's speech before the FSM sit-in [excerpt]. Free Speech Movement Archives. Retrieved from http://www.fsm-a.org/stacks/mario/mario_speech.html.
- Silver-Greenberg, J. (16 March 2011). Welcome to debtor's prison, 2011 edition. *Wall Street Journal*. Retrieved from <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424052748704396504576204553811636610.html>.
- Sinclair, U. (1922). *The goose step*. Pasadena, CA: Upton Sinclair.
- Sinclair, U. (1924). *The goslings: A study of the American schools*. Pasadena, CA: Upton Sinclair.
- Spivey, D. (1978). *Schooling for the new slavery: Black industrial education, 1868-1915*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Taussig, M. (1980). *The devil and commodity fetishism in South America*. Chapel Hill, NC: The University of North Carolina Press.
- Urban, W. & Wagoner, J. (2004). *American education: A history*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Westbrook, R. (2005). *Democratic hope: Pragmatism and the politics of truth*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

Notes

¹ An earlier version of this paper was presented at the Society for the Philosophical Study of Education annual conference in Chicago, Illinois, November 5, 2010.